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“BUYING GREEN OR BUYING IMAGE? CONSUMER MOTIVATION GAPS IN SUSTAINABLE MARKETS”

Buying green reflects a person's purchasing behavior and motives to protect the environment. Buying images also projects the status of a person's consciousness towards sustainable products. What drives a person to buy green products? It will start on beliefs and commitment because of the person's environmental concern. I wanted to help in a simple way to address climate change and pollution because I believe that everyone is responsible for protecting our environment to preserve our natural resources for future generations. As a consumer with strong commitment to buying green has the willingness to pay premium prices even though no one is seeing.

On the other hand, consumers buy green because of the image they wanted to project in the public showing that they are responsible for the environment and that is extrinsic buying motivation – a status symbol but it already defeats the purpose of buying green.

The role of marketers in this aspect is very important to guide the consumers whether they buy for values or for image so that the sustainability of buying green is not questionable that leads to green fatigue but remains their willingness to pay premium prices.

Buying green varies when we talk on socio-demographic influences for motivations across consumer segments. For example, the age between older and Gen Z both have different buying images. For consumers with high incomes, they can pay premium prices compared to a consumer with middle income. Another also is education, a consumer with high environmental literacy tends to be tied up with lifestyle purely in green products compared to a consumer with low environmental literacy.

In general, many consumers support green marketing in principle but, due to inflation, fewer follow when prices rise. This is called the attitude-behavior gap of consumers. They may want to buy green products, but convenience, price, and availability often override the intention.

In emerging markets for cultural and regional context, practical needs always outweigh environmental ideals. Green products may be seen as luxury goods and not for values, so the attitudes of consumers control green buying.

In this scenario, I try to see the implications for businesses. Understanding motivation helps firms to design a better strategy for consumers buying green and that is for values over consumers buy image. Firms have the role of emphasizing impact transparency and show measurable environmental benefits for green products.

Consumers may buy green products to balance the guilt rather than transform into their lifestyles. In this way, consumers buying behavior is symbolic rather than systematic and sometimes competes with convenience. Example, there is a high adoption to green products if cheaper and accessible and there is a low adoption of green products if it is costly and inconvenient. The most serious is consumer resistance if green products require lifestyle change.

The importance of role habit formation of consumers may sustain purchases if they evolve into habits. It may start with friends, trial purchase, then repeated purchases until the consumer already internalizes the values of buying green products.

In summary, the question of buying green versus buying image is not opposed but it is evolutionary, both are shaped into sustainable markets.

